

AI-assisted electrochemical detection of bacteria siderophores in clinical samples

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ABSTRACT

The rapid detection of bacteria remains a significant challenge in clinical contexts, with consequences for both patients and the medical system. While the electrochemical sensors deliver fast results, the matrix effect in real samples and the overlaps of the electrochemical signals are still of major concern and cannot be overcome in the absence of biorecognition elements and samples pretreatment protocols. The implementation of portable sensors in this case has promising potential, but their use is still limited to laboratory settings. An innovative approach is to develop an AI-assisted electrochemical sensor that employs machine learning algorithms to classify the target signal and overcome the interferences from real samples with complex biological matrices. The electrochemical behavior of three bacterial markers for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Escherichia coli* was analyzed in human serum to estimate the impact of any potential interference, whether from the environment or between components. Chemometrics have been used to evaluate the influence that the markers have on each other's analytical signals in the case of their simultaneous detection. A Decision Tree Classifier algorithm has been applied to enhance the sensitivity and improve the accuracy of the classification in cases of complex samples with promising results on real clinical samples.

1. Introduction

The rapid identification of bacteria in biological matrices is still a challenge of clinical diagnosis with a societal impact in the century of fast responses. Conventional methods like the classic microbiological plate culturing involve a lengthy time and complicated protocols and deliver a response in 48 to 72 h. However, in clinical life-threatening contexts, rapid intervention is often needed due to the patient's status, and thus, broad-spectrum antibiotics are frequently empirically administered [1]. The diagnostic and monitoring of a patient's health status employs a wide variety of biological samples, including blood (whole blood, serum, plasma), urine, feces, tissues, and other fluids (e.g., amniotic fluid, bronchoalveolar lavage), depending on the purpose of the assay. These samples have varying degrees of invasiveness depending on the sampling method, with the most examined ones being serum and urine, which can also provide information regarding the analyte

levels (pathogens or xenobiotics) and insight into the physiology of various organs [2].

Electrochemical methods can be a promising approach for developing new alternative analytical techniques for the detection of various compounds of medical interest, such as drugs, metabolites and even pathogenic agents, like viruses or bacteria [3]. Despite the promising results related to this approach, the complex biological matrices remain challenging in delivering a satisfying analytical result, mostly because of the numerous interferences that can alter the target signal and influence the detection limit. When analyzing real samples, the interference issue is an important point in the sensors' development outcome. While all the studies performed in laboratory-controlled settings are often predictable, with good analytical performances, the situation is different when biological samples are included due to the presence of other electrochemically active molecules with overlapping signals or insulating compounds [4,5]. Despite the varied strategies employed to minimize

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the matrix effect, like dilution, protein centrifugation and filtration, the results are still influenced by the complex matrix.

Statistical tools are an essential topic in the development and validation of electrochemical sensors, as they can optimize and enhance the analytical performance by assessing raw data provided by electrochemical experiments [6]. Chemometrics enable the analysis of large datasets while minimizing the number of necessary experiments, allowing prediction models that can discriminate the target analytes with high accuracy [7].

In this case, artificial-intelligence (AI) tools can provide more information than electrochemical experimental data can achieve. Starting from classification tasks and prediction tasks, AI-assisted electrochemical sensors can have an input in increasing the analytical performance and minimizing the interference rate and matrix effect [8,9]. The complex electrochemical fingerprint signals can be evaluated by filtering out the noise to increase the signal-to-noise ratio, thereby improving sensitivity, selectivity, and reliability [10]. When applied to the electrochemistry field, there are several points to be addressed, as follows: the number of samples for the training set needs to be large enough to guarantee the training of the algorithms, the high accuracy of the experiments, and the high reproducibility of data [11]. The main concern is to develop algorithms that can be implemented on small datasets, with an explainable decision process [12].

AI involvement in healthcare applications has the advantage of assessing trends and patterns that are difficult to be achieved due to the large amount of available experimental and clinical data [13–15]. Applications of ML-based electrochemical sensors are essential in biomedical applications for the detection of various analytes: the rabies virus [16], lidocaine [17], haemoglobin [18], glucose [19]; food industry for classifying pesticides, identifying heavy metals, pharmaceuticals, bacteria, antibiotics [20–22], and validating water quality [23,24], but also for the police forces, through the detection of illicit drugs in the case of seizures [25].

As for bacteria detection with AI-assisted sensors, the colorimetric and fluorescent techniques are mainly employed, while data from studies using electrochemical methods are still limited. The differentiation between G(–) and G(+) bacteria was performed using a colorimetric sensor under 60 min when an algorithm (YOLOv5) was utilized to analyze the signal colours acquired by a smartphone [26]. Furthermore, three bacterial species, *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*), *S. epidermidis*, and *Cutibacterium acnes* were identified by super-resolution fluorescence imaging and AI analysis from skin samples with very promising results for developing novel and faster detection strategies [27]. An electrochemical sensor based on gallium-indium alloy and natural hydrogel platform for the rapid detection (30 min) of *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) was also reported. The results were processed by ML models and demonstrated a high degree of accuracy when testing complex food samples [28]. An impedimetric sensor for the detection of three bacteria, *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* was developed, and the parameters of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) were used as input data to a random forest algorithm as a bacteria classifier. Hence, the bacteria were selected and optimized to construct a bacterial classifier that enabled the qualitative/semi-quantitative concomitant detection of the three pathogenic strains [29].

A novel study on the simultaneous detection of three bacterial metabolites: pyocyanin (PyoC), aerobactin (AeB), and enterobactin (EnB) as markers for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*K. pneumoniae*), and *E. coli* based on AI-assisted electrochemical sensors was developed in this study. By integrating ML algorithms with electrochemical fast detection, this system proposes a high-throughput and cost-effective solution for the identification of three different pathogen bacteria in complex real samples. To our knowledge, this is the first time when AI systems are employed to identify the presence of these markers as an indicator of bacteria presence, using the raw data issued from the electrochemical experiments.

2. Material and methods

All the reagents were used as received, with no treatment prior to the experiments. $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$, $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$, Na_2HPO_4 , NaH_2PO_4 , KCl, PyC, EnB, and the commercial human serum (cHS) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) and AeB was supplied by Boc Sciences (London, UK). The electrochemical studies were carried on screen-printed electrodes (SPEs) with graphite, graphene, mesoporous carbon (MC) and ordered-mesoporous carbon (OMC) working surfaces (having a geometric surface area of 12.56 mm^2), silver reference electrodes and carbon counter electrodes (Metrohm-DropSens, Spain).

2.1. Electrochemical study

The samples for the chemometric plan (optimization and characterization) were used without pretreatment or purification steps. The standard solutions of PyoC, AeB and EnB were prepared in cHS un/diluted in different ratios (1/10 and 1/50) with 20 mM saline phosphate buffer (PBS) pH 7.4, containing Na_2HPO_4 , NaH_2PO_4 , NaCl and KCl. The differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) experiments were carried out on SensiBT portable potentiostat from PalmSens B.V. (Houten, The Netherlands) paired with the dedicated software application PStace v.5.11. For the DPV procedures the potential was scanned from -0.9 V to 0.9 V , using a scan rate of 0.05 V/s . OriginPro 2022 (OriginPro v2023b, Number: GF3S5–6089-7,180,903) (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, MA, USA) was used for data analysis and BioRender for figures design.

2.2. Chemometrics

The influence of PyoC, AeB, EnB concentration levels and serum dilution factor on the Peak potential, Current Intensity and Peak Area was investigated by using a D-optimal experimental design with 29 runs and a G-efficiency of 67 %. The measurements were performed on two potential ranges, namely -0.5 to -0.3 V and 0.1 V corresponding to the anodic oxidation of PyoC/AeB and EnB.

The samples were prepared according to the factor combinations presented in Table 1. Using multiple linear regression, the response variation was modelled by considering the controlled variation of independent variables by fitting polynomial equations. Model interpretation was aided by representing the coefficients of equation terms, and by mapping the response variation using surface contour plots. Model performance was evaluated with respect to the percentage of explained response variability (R^2), predictive capacity (Q^2), model validity and reproducibility. ANOVA tests were applied to evaluate model significance and lack of fit. Data analysis was performed using Modde 13.1 Software (Sartorius Stedim Biotech, Germany).

Table 1
Independent and dependent variables defined in the experimental design.

Variables	Type	Settings
Independent variables		
PyoC	Multilevel	0, 25, 50, 100
AeB		0, 25, 50, 100
EnB		0, 25, 50, 100
Dilution		0.02, 0.1, 1
Dependent variables		
$E_{PyoC-AeB}/V$	Quantitative	
$I_{PyoC-AeB}/\mu A$		
$A_{PyoC}/\mu A$		
E_{EnB}/V		
$I_{EnB}/\mu A$		
A_{EnB}		

2.3. AI tools

2.3.1. Dataset description

The model was trained on laboratory generated samples, while the testing was done on real samples from bacteria cultures and consisted of samples prepared in 1/50 cHS and assessed by DPV. The electrochemical raw data consisted in a set of points forming a curve that is two dimensional (X-axis: 373 potential values ranging from -0.899 to $+0.898$ V/Ag, with an average step size of 0.005 V and Y-axis containing the corresponding values for the current intensity (μ A). The training dataset contained 51 unique samples, each one a combination of PyoC (0, 50, 100, 200 μ M), AeB (0, 88.5, 177.1, 354.2 μ M), and EnB (0, 72.05, 144.1, 288.2 μ M). The first sample in the dataset corresponded to a blank cH serum (1/50 diluted), that was considered as a baseline. The blank signal was subtracted from all samples to improve the clarity of the signal.

The test dataset includes 32 real samples from clinical sources, in contrast to the training dataset, which solely comprises lab samples (52 samples). As previously described in section 2.1.1, the samples were collected from bacterial cultures after 24 h and 48 h from inoculation. In order to improve the signal detection and to better evaluate the performance of the model under changing condition, a set of samples has been artificially amplified with 100 μ M of the equivalent biomarker, as described in (Table 2). The raw data had the same features as described for the training dataset. Similar to the training set, the testing set includes a blank serum sample that is used as reference. For refining the signal-to-noise ratio and to highlight the relevant electrochemical responses, the reference signal is subtracted from the remaining 31 samples. The data was computed with Jupyter Notebook and the programming language was Python 3.6.8.

2.3.2. Feature extraction

16 features extracted from the voltammetric signals were organised into sets that allowed the development of several signal classification models. More details regarding the signal processing and the features obtained are included in the **Supplementary material**.

2.3.3. Classification and training

2.3.3.1. Dataset partitioning and label encoding. The data used was divided into two categories: a training category (laboratory samples), and a testing category (real samples). The training category was constructed by varying the concentrations of three markers: Pyoc, AeB, and EnB. The training dataset was constructed by systematically varying the concentrations of the three bacteria markers, as previously described section 2.3.1 Due to the combinatorial explosion resulting from multiple concentration levels for each marker (leading to 64 possible combinations), and the limited number of actual samples (51), the use of one-hot encoding was impractical. Instead, a bin-based discretization strategy was adopted. Each concentration value was assigned to a specific bin, with bin indices increasing proportionally with concentration:

- PyoC: [0, 50, 100, 200] \rightarrow Bins [0,1,2,3].
- AeB: [0, 88.5, 177.1, 354.2] \rightarrow Bins [0, 1, 2, 3].
- EnB: [0, 72.05, 144.1, 288.2] \rightarrow Bins [0, 1, 2, 3].

Table 2
Samples included in the testing dataset.

Bacteria	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>		<i>K. pneumoniae</i>		<i>E. coli</i>	
Time after inoculation	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h
Number of samples	2	3	2	3	2	2
Bacteria	+100 μ M PyoC		+100 μ M AeB		+100 μ M EnB	
+100 μ M marker						
Time after inoculation	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h
Number of samples	3	3	2	3	3	3

A set of 16 features was extracted from each voltammogram. Due to the small size of the dataset, a comprehensive search was possible, by generating all categories of features (65,536 combinations). Each category of features was used to train a Decision Tree Classifier in order to deliver the best possible marker classification. This type of classifier was chosen due to its efficiency on small datasets. The model was trained on laboratory samples and tested on real samples (derived from the bacteria cultures 24 h and 48 h post inoculation).

2.3.3.2. Feature evaluation and model validation. The evaluation of the feature combination was achieved by comparing the predicted concentrations (in each bin) of PyoC, AeB, EnB, from patient samples, with the manually marked "ground truth" values. The emphasis was placed on those real samples spiked with 100 μ M of each marker and measured 48 h apart and were considered as the baseline for comparison.

The manual labelling was performed based on the known experimental conditions:

- *P. aeruginosa* (Pyo): Pyo bin = 1–3; AeB = 0; EnB = 0.
- *K. pneumoniae* (AeB): AeB bin = 1–3; PyoC = 0; EnB = 0.
- *E. coli* (EnB): EnB bin = 1–3; PyoC = 0; AeB = 0.

Of all the feature categories generated and evaluated, the following three categories provided the highest accuracy in classifying the reference experiments:

1. AUC, max peak X, number of peaks, median, kurtosis, rise time, first peak time, dominant frequency, area after peak
2. AUC, max peak X, max peak Y, number of peaks, median, skewness, kurtosis, signal energy, rise time, first peak time, dominant frequency, spectral entropy Y, area after peak Y, number of inflection points
3. AUC, max peak X, number of peaks, mean, skewness, kurtosis, rise time

These feature categories provided the highest congruence between presumed and actual concentrations of the biomarkers in real samples.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Electrochemistry

The first step was to assess the electrochemical behavior of AeB on different electrode surfaces (graphite, graphene, MC, OMC) to determine the suitable surface for the detection of the three analytes considered (PyoC, AeB, and EnB). Based on previous studies, the SPEs with graphite-based working surface were suitable for both PyoC and EnB [30,31], but the electrochemical fingerprint of AeB has not been documented yet. The signal of AeB was assessed on SPEs having graphite, graphene, MC and OMC as working surfaces. As can be seen from Fig. 1A, only a small anodic peak around -0.3 V/Ag observed on the OMC surface could be attributed to the anodic oxidation of AeB. As the electrochemical behavior for PyoC and EnB on graphite surface was similar to that on OMC, it was possible to continue the study on a suitable material for all three virulence markers.

The electrochemical behavior of the three compounds, individually or in different combinations, in cHS (undiluted and 1/10 and 1/50 dilutions in 20 mM PBS pH 7.4) was assessed to evaluate the effect of the dilution ratio at various concentration levels on the electrochemical signal, as well as the way they interfere with each other's analytical signal.

When analyzing the DPV signal obtained for 100 μ M PyoC in undiluted and 1/10, 1/50 diluted cHS (20 mM PBS pH 7.4), it can be clearly observed an anodic peak at around -0.35 V/Ag (Fig. 1B). Another smaller anodic peak was also noticed in the same potential range, in the

Fig. 1. DPVs in A. 100 μM AeB in 20 mM PBS pH 7.4 on different electrochemical surfaces; B. 100 μM PyoC in various cHS dilutions (undiluted, 1/10 and 1/50 with 20 mM PBS pH 7.4); C. 100 μM EnB in various cHS dilutions (undiluted, 1/10 and 1/50 with 20 mM PBS pH 7.4); D. 100 μM AeB in various cHS dilutions (undiluted, 1/10 and 1/50 with 20 mM PBS pH 7.4); E. Combinations of PyoC, AeB, and EnB in 1/50 cHS dilution in 20 mM PBS pH 7.4.

absence of any analyte, and it was attributed to the signal of the matrix. It was observed that the intensity of this signal proportionally decreased with the dilution level due to the matrix effect (cHS) that hindered the electron transfer rate. When a concentration of 100 μM AeB was tested in the same conditions as for PyoC, a low-intensity anodic signal was observed in the same potential range (around -0.35 V/Ag), different from the matrix effect (Fig. 1C). When PyoC and AeB were added to the same sample, it was not possible to distinguish between the two signals

observed during individual detection at about -0.35 V/Ag. The same observation was drawn when various combinations of AeB and PyoC concentrations and cHS dilutions were analyzed (Fig. 1E).

EnB, displayed an anodic peak at approximately 0.10 V/Ag without any visible interference with both PyoC and AeB. The signal increase was proportional to the dilution level and the analyte had the highest signal when the dilution level was 1/50 (Fig. 1D).

This configuration can successfully detect either PyoC and EnB or

AeB and EnB, however when both PyoC and AeB are found in the same samples they cannot be individually assigned. There is always the option to acquire selectivity by functionalizing the electrodes with nano-materials or biorecognition/affinity elements [32–35], but these approaches complicate the elaboration and testing protocols and lengthen the timeframe for a response.

3.1.1. Calibration curves

Based on the results obtained in un/diluted cHS, it was visible that the signal of the analytes increased with the dilution ratio. Consequently, all the electrochemical experiments were performed in 1/50 diluted cHS, as sample pretreatment. From Fig. 2 it can be seen that the signal of the analytes increased proportionally with their concentration.

The sensitivity of the method is comparable for both PyoC and EnB, however, for AeB the signal intensity was lower and the linear range narrower.

To better assess the influence of the analyte concentration and cHS dilution levels on the electrochemical signal, a chemometrics protocol was implemented using the acquired raw data.

3.1.2. Real samples analysis

Electrochemical experiments were performed on *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* cultures 24 h/48 h after their inoculation in 1/50 diluted cHS. Hence, two (*P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae*) and three (*E. coli*) bacteria colonies were suspended in 1/50 diluted cHS and the voltammograms were registered in the same conditions as mentioned above.

In the case of *P. aeruginosa* (Fig. 3A), an anodic peak can be observed at -0.38 V/Ag corresponding to the electrochemical oxidation of PyoC synthesized by the bacteria suspended in 1/50 diluted cHS after 24 h/48 h from inoculation. The samples were then spiked with $100 \mu\text{M}$ PyoC (1/50 diluted cHS) and the intensity of the peaks significantly increased. The signal of the real samples was compared with the current intensity of $100 \mu\text{M}$ PyoC standard solution (1/50 diluted cHS) and recoveries of 84.69 % (RSD 8.79 %) and 56.17 % (RSD 1.91 %) were reported after 24 h/48 h hours. The low recovery rates after 48 h can be associated with the accumulation of the bacteria strains and the viability of the bacteria that hindered the electron transfer rate and reduced the amplitude of the peaks.

P. aeruginosa cultures hit the stationary phase within 12–24 h when the highest current intensity for PyoC was observed. The concentration slightly decreased in the case of the decline phase where the viability of bacteria is starting to diminish, confirming the decrease in the current intensity of PyoC when 48 h cultures were analyzed [36]. The anodic shift with 0.3 V observed in the case of the spiked culture samples can be determined by the differences between the OMC electrodes and has no significant consequence on the peak intensity.

The same trend was observed when *K. pneumoniae* cultures were studied following the same protocol. The anodic current of AeB oxidation was observed in the same potential range -0.37 – -0.34 V/Ag as for PyoC. When the samples were spiked with $100 \mu\text{M}$ AeB standard solution (1/50 diluted cHS), the current intensity was higher, with 97.62 % (RSD 20.93 %) and 54.32 % (RSD 3.38 %) recoveries after 24 h and 48 h (Fig. 3B). Literature studies showcased the fact that the synthesis of

Fig. 2. Calibration curves in 1/50 diluted cHS (20 mM PBS pH 7.4) for A. Pyoc, B. AeB, and C. EnB.

Fig. 3. DPVs in A. *P. aeruginosa* colonies suspended in 1/50 cHS 24 h, respectively 48 h after inoculation in the presence of 100 µM PyoC; B. *K. pneumoniae* colonies suspended in 1/50 cHS at 24 h, respectively 48 h after inoculation in the presence of 100 µM AeB; C. *E. coli* colonies suspended in 1/50 cHS at 24 h, respectively 48 h after inoculation in the presence of 100 µM EnB; (for all the samples the cHS was diluted with 20 mM PBS pH 7.4); D. *P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae* colonies (1:1) suspended in 1/50 cHS at 48 h after inoculation.

siderophores is increased in the stationary phase and the trend continues along with diminishing the bacteria viability when survival mechanisms are activated due to the decrease of the iron availability, the same as our results obtained on the study of AeB, the siderophore of *K. pneumoniae*, when the signal increased after 48 h [37].

After mixing the two bacteria suspensions (1:1 ratio), the current intensity recorded at -0.3 V/Ag was approximately the sum of the signals corresponding to both PyoC and AeB (Fig. 3D).

In the case of the *E. coli* cultures, only a slight signal was observed at 0.1 V/Ag on the cultures inoculated from 24 h, but no signal was visible after 48 h. After spiking the sample with 100 µM EnB standard solution, the recoveries of the signal were approximately 93.45 % (RSD 8.83 %) and 67 % (RSD 4.28 %) after 24 h and 48 h, respectively (Fig. 3C).

The electrochemical data (potential, current intensity and recovery/RSD) are presented in Table 3.

After 24 h the bacteria exponential growth phase is over and is followed by the stationary phase characterized by nutrient depletion, waste accumulation and the rate of cell division slows down and equals with the rate of cell death [38]. Due to the accumulation of death bacteria cells, acting as waste, the electronic transfer rate is hindered, explaining the fact that the recoveries obtained after 48 h are significantly reduced with 25–40 % compared to those obtained for the 24-h culture samples.

3.2. Chemometrics

Based on the electrochemical experiments the measurements were performed in two potential ranges -0.5 – -0.3 V/Ag, and 0–0.1 V/Ag corresponding to the anodic oxidation of PyoC/AeB and EnB and current intensity, peak area, and peak potential parameters were assessed. The ANOVA test applied to evaluate regression significance revealed a statistically significant difference between the modelled and unmodelled response variation ($p < 0.05$), meaning that the response variation could be explained through the varied factors. All the models presented a decent predictive capacity (Q2) and explained a high amount of response variation (R2) (Table 4). The excellent reproducibility suggests appropriately designed experimental procedures. Model validity and lack of fit ($P > 0.05$) criterion was satisfied for all, except for Y6. In this case, a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was identified between model error and the replicate error, being caused by the very high reproducibility.

The coefficient column plots corresponding to Y1–2-3 (regarding the PyoC/AeB behavior) are presented in Fig. 4A. This set of response variables is influenced only by PyoC. An increase of PyoC from the lower to the higher concentration level (0 to 100 µM), while having all the other factors at intermediate level, will lead to a cathodic peak potential shift

Table 3
Analytical parameters obtained on real samples.

Bacteria type / Parameters	Ep (V/Ag)	I (μA)	Recovery (%) RSD (%)	Number of bacterial cells/ml	
24 h					
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	culture	-0.378	5.2	-	42.8 × 10 ⁶
	+100 μM PyoC	-0.41	67.1	89.00 (9.23)	
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	culture	-0.349	3.12	-	48.9 × 10 ⁶
	+100 μM AeB	-0.373	12.7	97.62 (20.93)	
<i>E. coli</i>	culture	-	-	-	58.2 × 10 ⁶
	+100 μM EnB	0.111	58.44	93.45 (8.83)	
48 h					
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	culture	-0.344	3.12	-	30.9 × 10 ⁶
	+100 μM PyoC	-0.373	42.35	56.17 (5.45)	
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	culture	-0.339	4.18	-	37.0 × 10 ⁶
	+100 μM AeB	-0.349	7.07	54.32 (3.52)	
<i>E. coli</i>	culture	-	-	-	41.2 × 10 ⁶
	+100 μM EnB	0.111	41.96	67.08 (4.28)	

with 0.0246 V, and an increase in $I_{\text{PyoC-AeB}}$ (Y2) and $A_{\text{PyoC-AeB}}$ (Y3) with 0.282 μA, respectively 0.294 V μA, confirming the electrochemical observations. The dilution factor has a positive influence on $E_{\text{PyoC-AeB}}$ (Y1), meaning that undiluted cHS will determine an anodic shift of the peak potential suggesting that the oxidation of the PyoC is reduced by the components of the matrix. The insignificant effect of AeB, even though it has a contribution in the same potential region, is a result of the low-intensity currents generated by this analyte, that are more visible when undiluted cHS is analyzed. This correlates to the results from the AeB calibration curve, where the slope/sensitivity was 5 times fold lower than for the other two analytes (Fig. 3B).

The coefficient plots corresponding to Y4–5–6 (regarding the EnB behavior) highlighted a similar correlation pattern with respect to the impact of EnB. An increase of EnB concentration from 0 to 100 μM, while having the other factors at intermediate level, will lead to a drop in peak potential with 0.004 V (that is not analytical significant), and an increase in the I_{EnB} (Y5) and A_{EnB} (Y6) with 9.833 μA, respectively 1.180 VμA. The nonsignificant effects identified for PyoC and AeB confirm the absence of any interferences regarding EnB identification, supporting the electrochemical observations. The dilution factor exerted a positive effect on E_{EnB} and a negative effect on I_{EnB} and A_{EnB} . This observation is to be expected because when the dilution is at the highest level (1/50), the matrix effect is reduced (as can be seen from Fig. 4B), while when the undiluted cHS is used, the intensity of the current is greatly diminished, as observed for both PyoC/AeB.

The surface contour plots described efficiently the dependence of EnB exerted effects in function of the applied dilution. For highly diluted

Table 4
Model performance parameters.

	R2	Q2	Validity	Reproducibility	ANOVA regression	ANOVA lack of fit
Y1- $E_{\text{PyoC-AeB}}/V$	0.628	0.505	0.719	0.909	9.69e-04	3.26e-01
Y2- $I_{\text{PyoC-AeB}}/\mu A$	0.894	0.795	0.345	0.989	6.30e-11	7.33e-02
Y3- $A_{\text{PyoC-AeB}}/V\mu A$	0.749	0.637	0.300	0.979	7.90e-07	6.12e-02
Y4- E_{EnB}/V	0.465	0.351	0.308	0.957	1.15e-03	6.30e-02
Y5- $I_{\text{EnB}}/\mu A$	0.835	0.743	0.252	0.988	2.60e-08	5.05e-02
Y6- $A_{\text{EnB}}/V\mu A$	0.811	0.711	0.130	0.992	1.21e-07	3.09e-02

cHS samples (1/50), an increasing level of EnB has a minimal effect on E_{EnB} , whereas for undiluted samples the E_{EnB} shifts from 0.12 to 0.095 as the EnB content is increased (Fig. 4C). This issue can be also determined by the variability of the electrodes' surfaces and has no influence on the electrochemical signal of EnB since there are no other compounds of interest in this potential range. For I_{EnB} and A_{EnB} , a strong increase of the response variable is recorded with increasing EnB level for highly diluted samples (1/50) (Fig. 4E). As expected, in the case of undiluted cHS samples, I_{EnB} and A_{EnB} have only a minimum variation due to the matrix effect.

3.3. AI tools

In order to determine the model's performance, two sets of estimates were made, both using the Decision Tree Classifier (DTC) algorithm. Although both evaluations used accuracy as the primary measurement performance, the method of calculating it varied, contingent on the type of dataset. In order to classify both laboratory and real samples, the following combination of features (with the greatest coefficient of discretization) was used: AUX, Max Peak on X axis, Number of Peaks, Median, Kurtosis, Rise Time, First Peak Time, Dominant Frequency, Area after Peak.

3.3.1. Performance evaluation on the laboratory dataset

Accuracy was calculated for each bacteria marker - PyoC, AeB, EnB – and the predictions were assessed independently. A prediction was considered to be accurate if the predicted bin value concurred with the value of the actual bin. This allowed to check how the model performed for each marker. The laboratory dataset was randomly split into a training dataset and a testing dataset using an 80/20 ratio. The performance of the model was assessed using values that reflected the accuracy for each individual marker rather than that for the entire sample.

3.3.2. Accuracy (Exact bin match)

For each bacteria marker – Pyoc, AeB, EnB – the prediction was considered accurate only if the predicted bin coincided with the actual bin in the test set. The results were as follows: 63 % accuracy for Pyo (7/11 bins correctly predicted), 45 % accuracy for AeB (5/11 bins correctly predicted), and 36 % accuracy for EnB (4/11 bins correctly predicted) (Table 5).

If the accuracy had been measured for each individual sample, requiring all 3 markers to be correctly recognised in a sample, the results would have been significantly weaker since only one sample out of the 11 had all of the biomarkers predicted correctly. The data on PyoC displayed higher accuracy, while for AeB and EnB lower values PyoC outperforms AeB and EnB, because features like area after peak, kurtosis and rise time provide a higher discretization coefficient, implied by the pure leaf nodes (gini = 0) in the decision tree and also how quickly gini reaches 0. EnB and AeB could probably perform better, by using another classifier (Random Forest, Gradient Boosting) or by extracting other features (see **Supplementary material**). Other performance metrics (Precision, Recall, and F1-score) have been computed for each biomarker and are in agreement with the accuracy data. These metrics were calculated per class, using a one-versus-rest strategy, then averaged across all classes (macro average). For example, PyoC achieved the

Fig. 4. Coefficient column plots revealing the influence of independent variables on A. Y1-Y2-Y3; B. Y4-Y5-Y6; C.-E. Surface contour plots highlighting the interaction between EnB and dilution level for Y4-5-6.

Table 5

Performance evaluation on the laboratory dataset.

Parameters	PyoC	AeB	EnB
Accuracy	63.6 %	45.4 %	36.3 %
Precision (macro)	75 %	27.5 %	29.1 %
Recall (macro)	72.9 %	41.6 %	33.3 %
F1-score (macro)	61.4 %	33 %	22.7 %
Alternative accuracy	100 %	90.9 %	81.8 %

following: **Accuracy = 0.6364 (63.6%)**, with 7 out of 11 correct predictions. **Macro-Precision = 0.7500 (75 %)**, averaged from per-class precision values [0.75, 1.00, 0.25, 1.00]. **Macro-Recall = 0.7292 (72.9 %)**, averaged from per-class recall values [1.00, 0.67, 1.00, 0.25]. **Macro-F1 = 0.6143 (61.4 %)**, averaged from per-class F1 values [0.86, 0.80, 0.40, 0.40].

3.4. Alternative accuracy (± 1 Bin margin)

It was noticed that most of the incorrect predictions were within 1 bin level of the actual value. Despite the finding that the model did not correctly predict the exact bin value, the prediction was still close enough. After recalculating the accuracy with a tolerance of $+ - 1$ bin, where predictions are thought to be correct if the predicted bin value differs from the actual bin value by one unit, the following results were obtained: for PyoC 100 % accuracy (7 exact matches, 4 within ± 1), for AeB 90.9 % accuracy (5 exact matches, 5 within ± 1), while for EnB 81.8 % accuracy (4 exact matches, 5 within ± 1). This alternative measurement made room for the possibility of a more lenient assessment of the model's performance and the subsequent accuracy of the results from evaluating the real-world samples (Table 5).

3.4.1. Results on real samples

In contrast to the laboratory dataset, accuracy was calculated for each sample. A prediction was considered to be accurate only if all of the three markers were correctly classified – meaning that the predicted bins for PyoC, AeB and EnB were equal in value to the actual bin values for the corresponding sample. This measurement, more rigorous than the previous one, guaranteed that the whole composition of the sample (all markers) was correctly recognised, without having to predict the exact concentration.

Each real sample was associated with one of the following three bacterial cultures:

- *P. aeruginosa*: PyoC present (bin 1, 2, or 3), AeB and EnB absent (bin 0).
- *K. pneumoniae*: AeB present, Pyo and EnB absent (bin 0).
- *E. coli*: EnB present, PyoC and AeB absent (bin 0).

The model was trained on a laboratory dataset, using a Decision Tree Classifier wrapped in a MultiOutputClassifier, using the optimal feature subset. The model was then tested on the real samples dataset. More details regarding the feature importance hierarchy and DTC model for the three biomarkers are included in the **Supplementary material**.

In the first stage of the evaluation were analyzed the culture samples spiked with 100 μM marker. The goal was to check if the model could aptly detect the presence of the correct marker, and the absence of those markers unrelated to the culture. Out of the 17 reference samples (spiked with 100 μM marker) the model correctly classified 16 (94.11 % accuracy). This confirmed the high sensitivity for the presence of a marker, when added in a known and controlled amount and can be included in the testing protocol. Performance was also analyzed on real bacteria culture samples without any added marker. These samples are inherently more difficult to classify due to weaker signal strength and higher biological variability. As expected, classification performance declined in these samples, due to lower marker concentrations, which in turn affected the signal behavior and reduced the distinction between the features. The summary of performance was displayed in Fig. 5.

3.4.2. Improvement strategies

One major limitation of the current study was the small size of the training set, which contained only 52 samples. This limited data set did not cover all 64 possible combinations for the three biomarkers – PyoC, AeB and EnB – with bin values ranging from [0,0,0] to [3]. Some significant combinations, such as [3,3,0], [3,2,0] and [3], were missing from the dataset. This partial representation of the feature space reduced the capacity of the model to learn. Further studies are foreseen to generate a higher number of samples for more advanced approaches like ANN or CNN [39] rather than a ML algorithm. Although the use of a less advanced approach such as the DTC was justified given the small number of samples [40,41], using a larger dataset would have allowed the usage of more powerful modelling, thus improving the accuracy.

The DTC was selected for this study based on two key considerations: **the relatively small training dataset** (52 samples), thus limiting the use of more complex ML models, which normally require the use of a larger dataset and **the high discretization coefficient of the extracted features** (AUC, X-axis value corresponding to the maximum current peak, and Number of peaks), making it appropriate for tree-based classification.

The DTC can evaluate inputs without requiring normalization or scaling, thus simplifying preprocessing. The automatic feature selection process, which thoroughly evaluated all the possible feature groupings for training a DTC, can be extended by applying alternative algorithms such as XGBoost [42], which often outperforms other algorithms on tabular data and can handle feature interactions efficiently or **Support Vector Machines (SVMs)** [43], known for their performance on small to medium-sized datasets with well-separated classes.

In order to create a ML model, able to classify the real sample dataset, a number of common signal processing features were extracted. (Number of peaks, AUC, and the X-axis value corresponding to the maximum current peak). The models with the highest accuracy percentage used both common features, and less conventional features. The number of features could be increased, to improve overall performance of the model, by extracting new features, or combining the existing ones, such as *Max Peak Y / AUC* (the sharpness or dominance of the peak relative to total signal strength) or *AUC / Number of Peaks* (average signal contribution per peak).

4. Conclusions

The electrochemical detection of bacterial markers raises several issues regarding the signal overlaps and the influence of the matrix when assessing real samples. By using electrochemical sensors the signal of PyoC and AeB cannot be discriminated against, hence the simultaneous identification of *P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae* cannot be achieved. When the electrochemical data was analyzed using ML, the discrimination of the two signals was achieved. Given the small dataset, a DTC algorithm was trained to deliver the best possible bacterial marker classification. The algorithm was trained on the laboratory experiments and tested on the real samples with promising results.

The main contribution of this work underlines the association of ML and electrochemical sensors for the simultaneous detection of three bacteria. When compared to the classical and traditional methods of detecting the previously mentioned pathogens, the proposed system detects in a matter of seconds the presence or the absence of all three pathogens. Additionally, the system is particularly sensitive to false negatives, which are more detrimental than false positives. Ongoing work can be performed in regard to the dataset, to enlarge it as much as possible so that the classification algorithms can learn better the behavior of each bacterial marker. Broadening the feature space—through both additional signal descriptors and intelligent feature engineering—could substantially enhance the model's predictive capacity. Combined with an expanded dataset and alternative classification algorithms, this approach holds promise for developing more accurate and generalizable models for biomarker detection in complex

Bacteria	PyoC	AeB	EnB
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 48 h Sample 1	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 48 h Sample 2	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 48 h Sample 3	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 48 h+ 100 µM PyoC Sample 1	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 48 h+ 100 µM PyoC Sample 2	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 48 h+ 100 µM PyoC Sample 3	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 24 h Sample 1	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 24 h Sample 2	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 24 h+ 100 µM PyoC Sample 1	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 2	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 24 h+ 100 µM PyoC Sample 2	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 2	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 24 h+ 100 µM PyoC Sample 3	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 2	Expected:0 Actual: 3	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> 48 h Sample 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> 48 h Sample 2	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> 48 h Sample 3	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> 48 h+100 µM AeB Sample 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> 48 h+100 µM AeB Sample 2	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> 48 h+100 µM AeB Sample 3	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> 24 h Sample 1	Expected:0 Actual: 3	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 2
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> 24 h Sample 2	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> 24 h+100 µM AeB Sample 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> 24 h+100 µM AeB Sample 2	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 3	Expected:0 Actual: 0
<i>E.coli</i> 48 h Sample 1	Expected:0 Actual: 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 3
<i>E.coli</i> 48 h Sample 2	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 1	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 0
<i>E.coli</i> 48 h + 100 µM EnB Sample 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1
<i>E.coli</i> 48 h + 100 µM EnB Sample 2	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1
<i>E.coli</i> 48 h + 100 µM EnB Sample 3	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1
<i>E.coli</i> 24 h Sample 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 3
<i>E.coli</i> 24 h Sample 2	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1
<i>E.coli</i> 24 h + 100 µM EnB Sample 1	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 3
<i>E.coli</i> 24 h + 100 µM EnB Sample 2	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 3
<i>E.coli</i> 24 h + 100 µM EnB Sample 3	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected:0 Actual: 0	Expected: [1,2,3] Actual: 1

Fig. 5. Results after applying the DTC model on the real samples.

biological signals.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ana-Maria Tataru: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal

analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marius-Adrian Stoica:** Validation, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Andreea Cernat:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Anda Falau:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Adrian Groza:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis,

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2025.115695>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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